

Distance Education for the History Unit of the 3rd Grade of the Elementary School “Theseus”

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Abstract: Environment using the distance education method for the History course in the 3rd grade of the Primary School for the unit “The Theseus”. The article consists of three parts. The first one presents the theoretical framework in which Distance School Education refers, the basic principles of creating the educational material, more specifically Mayer’s principles on which the creation of the material was based, and the relationship of ICT with History. This material is recommended as a supplementary tool for the teacher or as a supporting tool for the students’ independent learning. Firstly, the technical means of creating the educational material are mentioned (H5P tools, Chamilo). After the presentation of the material follows the second part in which reference is made to the methodological approach of the research. In both parts of the research, qualitative research of formative evaluation is used as a tool of the questionnaire of open and closed questions. Content analysis was used for the methodological approach to data processing with the unit of analysis being the semantically autonomous vocabulary. Important conclusions emerge from the research. Experts argue that the material is governed by the principles and methodology of Distance Education (scientific coherence — documentation, contributes to the simple-understandable presentation of the knowledge object, is easy to use, supports — guides the learner, supports interaction, provides the possibility of reflection — self-assessment, covers purpose — expected learning outcomes). They also judged that it is in line with the Principles of Multimedia Learning. The teachers argued that the material meets the objectives of the Study program and there is validity in its content. All indicated that they would choose the specific material in the context of teaching the “Theseus” unit. Finally, it is necessary to mention the limitations of the research. Firstly, the non-use of the material for evaluation by the students and secondly, the research sample is small and the results are not generalizable.

Key words: school distant education, didactic history – mythology, educational material for distant teaching

1. Introduction

Distance education is inextricably linked with ICT Information and Communication Technologies. With their help, communication between stakeholders is supported. In addition, it helps in the creation of electronic and

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digital material, the design of which is considered particularly important since it replaces the instructor (Lionarakis, 2006).

ICT is characterized as a tool that helps the instructor to organize a program or modify an existing one since it can be used in conjunction with printed material. It is argued that they can be used as a supporting tool of the educational project (Spantidakis & Vasarmidou, 2014).

It is useful to include ICT in the teaching of History. By using Information and Communication Technologies in the History course, students will be able to develop their research skills, cultivate their historical thinking and develop attitudes and behaviors. In addition to students, however, teachers can also present their material in such a way that satisfies and fascinates every student (Tsortanidou, 2016).

This article presents the design, development and evaluation of educational material using the distance education method for 3rd grade students in the unit of the cognitive subject of History “Theseus”. This article is structured in three parts. In the theoretical framework, in the first part, Distance School Education, the basic principles of creating educational material and the relationship of ICT with the History course are mentioned. The methodological approach of the research follows in the second part. Finally, the third part presents the conclusions of the research process.

2. Theoretical Framework

2.1 School Distance Education

School distance education is defined as education that covers the needs of students at the level of Primary and Secondary education (Vasala, 2005).

Miminou and Spanaka (2013) distinguish school-based e-learning in three forms: a) independent school distance education, where its curricula are comprehensive but also equal to conventional education, giving the opportunity to learn to students who are excluded from conventional education due to their residence in remote areas, due to special needs, family-economic needs and due to age (Sofos, Kostas & Paraschou, 2015). b) The supplementary school distance education which follows the methods of the autonomous but works auxiliary and parallel to the conventional education. Supplementary school-based ED is used to attend individual courses for specific reasons by providing courses either outside the ALS Analytical Curriculum of conventional education intended to explore the learning content, or intended to reinforce conventional teaching, or for weak or gifted learners (Sofos, Kostas & Paraschou, 2015), either to complete tasks or teleconferences held by schools participating in the school networks. c) Mixed-combination-multimodal education combines conventional and distance education.

2.2 Educational Material in School Distance Education

The role of educational material in distance education, as shown in Figure 1, lies in the learning process, because the learner is led to learn through it and the instructor acts in a consultative-guiding manner (Mouzakis, 2006).

The educational material also has the role of guiding the learner in his study, explaining difficult points, animating and encouraging him to continue by assessing his progress and freely choosing place-time-rate of study (Lionarakis, 2009).

Banou (2001, op. ref. in Karagianni & Anastasiadis, 2009) states that EY has a dominant role in distance education being a “living learning set”. Therefore, the design and creation of educational material must follow

specific procedures and meet specific pedagogical specifications (Manousou, 2008).

Figure 1 The Educational Material in Distance Education

Source: Mouzakis, 2006

Mena (1992, op. ref. in Giosos & Koutsoumba, 2005) in order to develop a two-way, interactive and dialectical material suggests the following principles:

- Informing the trainees to understand the training material.
- Reflection through which learners correlate new data with knowledge and their own reality and deepen their knowledge of a specific subject area.
- Exchange and discussion to promote collaborative learning.
- Relativization of data where learners are asked to apply the new knowledge they have acquired in their own reality.
- Editing in order for the new knowledge to bring self-awareness to the trainees.
- Evaluation using a variety of methods. In this way, the trainees evaluate their progress and cultivate their ability to effectively solve similar problems.

Mayer (2017, op. ref. in Anastasiadis & Kotsidis, 2015) talks about the Principles of Multimedia Learning. In multimedia learning, there is talk of the correlation that exists in the effectiveness of learning and the ability of learners to develop relationships and links between visual and verbal representations in short-term memory (Mayer, 2005, op. ref. in Denmark, 2017). Mayer (2017, op. ref. in Anastasiadis & Kotsidis, 2015), therefore, in order for learning to be effective and active, he suggests that the design and organization of the educational material should follow the following Principles: Multimedia Principle (The presentation of information is done using simultaneously words and images. With this principle the information is better understood and processed more effectively by the learner), Principle of Spatial Relevance (Here an image is close to its related text. So learners have a better understanding of the message), Principle of Temporal Relevance (There is a simultaneous presentation of words-images. This simultaneous and not consecutive presentation helps the students to learn better), Principle of Coherence (The educational material is freed from unnecessary verbal and visual information. The deviation of information unrelated to the subject facilitates learner learning), Principle of Modality (In this principle, narration is used instead of quoting written texts), Principle of Redundancy (Avoid using multiple media to present the content due to overloading the educational material in this way), Principle of Personalization (In the

educational material there should be friendliness. It can be reinforced by using friendly language, second person, narration, visual cues, personal style, use of interactive skills), Principle of Segmentation (The summary and specific visual and auditory information of the educational material helps to preserve and store the information in the memory of the trainees), Principle of Signaling (In order for the attention of the trainees to be directed to the more substantial processing of the information, appropriate social and cognitive cues are provided), Principle of Pre-Education (An activity is given to learn knowledge and skills necessary to study the main part of the educational material), Principle of Voice (Politeness and friendliness in the voices of multimedia courses is considered necessary), Principle of Image (Does not necessarily provide any assistance to the learner or existence of the image of the narrator in the educational material).

2.3 ICT and History

According to Souma (q.v.) the use of ICT in the teaching of History makes the course modern, experiential, student-centered. In addition, it helps learners easily refer to historical sources, digital maps and diagrams. In this way, they become more observant, understand historical events and cultivate their memory capacity. Thus, the course attracts learners and motivates them to participate actively (Heafner, 2004).

It would be good to choose the appropriate methods and the appropriate tools for teaching it, helping students to cultivate their historical critical thinking, making them tomorrow’s responsible citizens (DEPPS-APS, 2003; Repoussi, 2004; Parafesta & Smyrniaios, 2020).

However, Mythology also belongs to the History course, bringing the students into contact with their cultural heritage (DEPPS-APS, 2003). Myths were created to interpret what people could not explain in any other way (Maistrellis, Kalyvi & Michael, 2011).

3. Description of Educational Material for the Unit “Theseus”

The design of the educational material for the History section of the 3rd grade of the Elementary School “The Theseus” was done in h5p, an open type software using Course Presentation in order to create the interactive presentations.

3.1 Technical Means of Creating Educational Material

The following means were used to create the EY:

- H5p tool: h5p is an open source online tool provided free of charge to create interactive content (videos, presentations...) in HTML5. Content created in h5p can be embedded into blogs and platforms. It is an ideal way to create editable learning objects.
- Chamilo Platform: A Learning Management System (LMS), is a free open source tool created to allow teachers to fully monitor student results, to change and improve if necessary their applied methodology.
- Plotagon: As a storytelling tool for all ages, Plotagon enables the creation of animated films.
- Blippar: Blippar is a platform that specializes in creating and publishing augmented reality content.

3.2 Presentation of Teaching Units

The basic menu of each teaching unit includes:

- The introductory elements of the module
- The main course
- Time to play (image 1, image 2)

Figure 2 Main Part of Teaching Modules

> ΣΚΟΠΟΣ
> ΠΡΟΣΔΟΚΩΜΕΝΑ ΜΑΘΗΣΙΑΚΑ ΑΠΟΤΕΛΕΣΜΑΤΑ
> ΔΟΜΗ ΕΝΟΤΗΤΑΣ
> ΛΕΞΕΙΣ ΚΛΕΙΔΙΑ
> ΧΡΟΝΟΣ ΜΕΛΕΤΗΣ
Reuse Embed

Figure 3 Introductory Data

3.2.1 Presentation of the 1st Teaching Unit: Theseus the King of Troizena

In the 1st teaching unit, the educational material focused on the chapter of the 3rd grade Elementary History book “Theseus, the king of Troizena” in order to make a first acquaintance with the hero and for the user to get to know some of his exploits. Upon entering, the user will navigate the course through slides where the necessary information is presented using interactive videos, hyperlinks, texts, interactive exercises and games. Some

snapshots from the 1st teaching unit are presented as examples.

Figure 4 Useful Tips

Figure 5 Contents

Figure 6 Summary

Figure 7 Evaluation Activity

3.2.2 Presentation of the 2nd Teaching Unit

In the 2nd teaching unit, the educational material focused on the section of the History book “Theseus kills the Minotaur” in order for the user to learn the reason Theseus kills the Minotaur. Upon entering, the user will navigate the course through slides where the necessary information is presented using interactive videos, hyperlinks, texts, interactive exercises and games. Some snapshots from the 2nd teaching unit are presented as examples.

Figure 8 Text With Blippar

Συμπλήρωσε τα κενά με τις λέξεις που λείπουν.

Μίνωα, Μινώταυρος, ανθρώπινο, Δαίδαλος, ταύρου, λαβύρινθο

Ο ήταν ένα τέρας με κεφάλι και σώμα . Ζούσε στον στο υπόγειο του παλατιού του . Τον λαβύρινθο τον είχε φτιάξει ο .

Έλεγχος

Για να το θυμηθείς μπορείς να πατήσεις [εδώ](#).

Figure 9 Activity

4. Methodology

4.1 Purpose of the Research

The purpose of this research is the evaluation of the supplementary educational material created by the distance education method for the teaching of the "Theseus" section of 3rd grade History both by distance education experts and by the research team consisting of teachers Primary Education.

4.2 Research Problem

The use of new technologies in the educational process makes its appearance in various forms, the most important of which is distance education. Its use began in higher education and is slowly being included in the other two levels of education. It is a method that works by combining pedagogy and technology without deeming it appropriate to have a live encounter between learner and instructor (Lionarakis, 2006) creating, as long as technology is utilized in pedagogical and social terms, collaborative distance learning environments that aim to encourage exploratory and critical thinking (Anastasiadis, 2009) but also to lead the learner to autonomy (Nikolaki & Koutsoumba, 2013).

A very important role in distance education is played by the educational material which helps the learner in his study from the moment he opens himself up to the role of a distance instructor (Rowntree, 1994), so according to Ropokis (2011) the way that is designed and developing educational material is one of the most important issues that concern distance education.

Regarding school supplementary distance education:

- It is a helper for activities that aim to understand the pre-existing knowledge of the trainees (Anastasiou, Androutsou & Georgalas, 2009).
- "It provides students with the opportunity to improve their level of knowledge, through solving a large number of exercises, simultaneously presenting them with the correct and incorrect answers in combination with the necessary explanations for both cases" (Anastasiou, Androutsou & Georgalas, 2010; Spantidakis, 2006, op. ref. in Anastasiadis, 2014, p. 10).
- "Supports students with learning difficulties" (Spantidakis, Mouzaki & Aggeli, 2008; Paleologu et al., 2004, op. ref. in Anastasiadis, 2014, p. 10).

The present work, utilizing the methodology of Distance Education for the design and development of educational material for the teaching of the "Thesis" section of History to 3rd grade students, tries to integrate ICT in the learning process and to make the material work as a complementary tool, supporting at the same time students' autonomous learning. The creation of the educational material was based on the principles of Multimedia Learning including interactive videos/books, images, activities, games in order to attract the students' interest in the History lesson. After all, the History we learned when we were children helps us understand the world around us (Ferro, 2016).

The choice of the third section of History entitled "Theseus" was not accidental. The specific section was chosen because it was established by the creator of the material that the children did not know this particular hero, unlike other heroes of Greek mythology. Moreover, this finding was not based on a single school year, but on several over the last 10 years.

4.3 Research Questions

The research questions posed in relation to the purpose and individual objectives are as follows:

- Is the educational material governed by the Principles and Methodology of distance education? (1st Research Question).
- Has the educational material been created according to the Principles of Multimedia Learning? (2nd Research Question).
- What are the opinions of Primary Education teachers about the educational material created for 3rd Primary students in the context of the cognitive subject of the third unit of History entitled “Theseus”? (3rd Research Question).

4.4 The Research Sample and Research Design

The sample of the first part of the research was 3 educational specialists in the methodology of distance education after they participated in the postgraduate program of the Pedagogical Department of Primary Education of the University of Crete entitled: “Educational Sciences — Distance Education with the use of ICT (e-learning)”. For the second part of the research, 5 Primary Education teachers were selected, specifically PE70 teachers from Heraklion prefecture who had teaching experience in 3rd Primary.

In the research of the first part, the method of “Qualitative Content Analysis” was used. The researcher, after giving them the electronic access link to the Chamilo platform, asked them after studying the educational material to submit their opinions in the questionnaire created for this purpose by E.D.I.B.E.A. (Laboratory of Advanced Learning Technologies in Lifelong Learning and Distance Education). This questionnaire includes closed and open questions. They were initially asked to answer seven closed-ended questions about their demographics and profile. They were then asked to answer fifty-six questions, open-ended, for the evaluation of the educational material, which are articulated in 9 axes (Table 1) corresponding to the research questions. For the investigation of the first two research questions, individual research axes were identified respectively. Specific questions in the questionnaire corresponded to each research axis, as shown in Table 2.

In the research of the second part, five Primary Education teachers were selected, specifically PE70 teachers who had teaching experience in the 3rd Primary. The “Qualitative Content Analysis” method was used in this research. The researcher, after giving them the electronic access link to the Chamilo platform, asked them to submit their opinions regarding the response of the educational material to the objectives of the Curriculum and the validity of the content. Thus, a questionnaire was created that includes closed and open type questions. They were initially asked to answer five closed-ended questions about their demographics and profile. They were then asked to answer eight questions, open-ended, to evaluate the educational material. To investigate the third research question, three individual axes were identified as shown in Table 3. Each research axis corresponded to specific questions in the questionnaire, as shown in Table 4.

Table 1 Survey of Distance Education Experts — Research Axes

1st Axis: Scientific coherence/Documentation of the Educational material
2nd Axis: The Educational material contributes to the simple and understandable presentation of the Knowledge Object
3rd Axis: Ease of use of the educational material.
4th Axis: The Educational material supports – guides the learner in his study
5th Axis: The Educational material supports the interaction with the learner in his study
6th Axis: The Educational material provides the possibility of Reflection - Self-Assessment to the learner
7th Axis: Purpose/ Expected Results
8th Axis: The Educational material is created according to the Principles of Multimedia Learning
9th Axis: General Notes

Table 2 Survey of Distance Education Specialists – Research Axes – Questions in Each Axis

1st Axis: A. Scientific Coherence/Documentation of the Educational Material
A.1 Information/opinions are quoted in the educational material with the relevant bibliographic documentation.
A.2 In the educational material, reference is made to different sources of information (Books, scientific journals, scientific conferences, etc.).
A.3 In the educational material, a comparative analysis of the information/opinions is done.
A.4 The educational material is enriched with the interpretation/critical discussion of the information.
A.5 The educational material provides the opportunity for the learner to study further in different sources.
2nd Axis: B. The Educational Material Contributes to the Simple and Understandable Presentation of the Knowledge Object
B.1 The writing style of the educational material is reader friendly.
B.2 Personal and possessive pronouns are used in the educational material.
B.3 In the educational material, the colloquial language is used whenever possible.
B.4 The writing of the educational material is easy to read.
B.5 The information density of the educational material is satisfactory.
B.6 The educational material is presented segmentally in the screen size.
B.7 The training material has only text.
B.8 The educational material contains text and images.
B.9 The educational material contains text, images and videos.
B.10 The color schemes of the educational material contribute to comfortable interaction.
3rd Axis: C. Usability of the Educational Material
C.1 The buttons used in the educational material (forward, back etc.) are understandable and recognizable.
C.2 The icons used in the educational material (additional resources, activities, etc.) are understandable and recognizable.
C.3 Navigating the learning material is easy.
C.4 Hyperlinks in the educational material lead to the expected content.
4th Axis: D. The Educational Material Supports — Guides the Learner in His Study
D.1 Advice is provided on how to study the training material.
D.2 The learning material supports the learner to emphasize specific points (There are boxes or bold text (marking) to highlight important concepts).
D.3 In the educational material there are explanatory comments which support the student in his study.
5th Axis: E. The Educational Material Supports the Interaction With the Learner in His Study
E.1 The educational material includes activities that encourage the learner to express their own opinions (judgments) on important issues.
E.2 The educational material includes activities that encourage the learner to formulate his own questions about important issues.
E.3 The educational material contains activities that encourage the learner to become emotionally involved based on his personal interests.
E.4 The educational material includes activities that encourage the learner to exchange opinions with other learners.
E.5 The educational material includes activities that encourage the learner to think of himself as a member of a social group that has specific needs and expectations.
E.6 The learning material includes activities which encourage the learner to integrate/enrich their views in it.
6th Axis: F. The Educational Material Provides the Possibility of Reflection — Self-Assessment for the Learner
F.1 The educational material includes activities that encourage self-evaluation of the learner.
F. 2 The educational material includes activities that encourage the development of the learner’s autonomous critical thinking.
F.3 The educational material includes activities that encourage the development of communication channels with the aim of providing feedback to the learner.
St.4 The educational material includes activities that encourage the learner to relate the new data to their own reality.
F.5 The educational material includes activities that encourage the learner to apply the new knowledge to their own reality.

(Table 2 to be continued)

(Table 2 continued)

7th Axis: G. Purpose/Expected Results	
G.1	The purpose of each teaching unit is clearly stated in the educational material.
G.2	The educational material clearly states the expected results in each teaching unit.
G.3	Expected outcomes motivate the learner at the level of knowledge.
G.4	Expected outcomes motivate the learner to skill level.
G.5	Expected outcomes motivate the learner at the attitudinal level.
G.6	The learner monitors his progress based on the expected results.
8th Axis: H. The Educational Material Has Been Created According to the Principles of Multimedia Learning	
H.1	In the educational material there is a combination of text and image for the presentation of the knowledge object. (Multimedia Authority)
H.2	In the educational material the use of images helps you to understand the subject. (Multimedia Authority)
H.3	In the educational material there are elements of narration (monologue, dialogue, description, comments, etc.). (Principle of Tropicality)
H.4	The educational material includes non-related information (words, images, sounds) with the subject. (Principle of Coherence)
H.5	Friendly language is used in the educational material. (Principle of Personalization)
H.6	In the educational material, second person is used. (Principle of Personalization)
H.7	In the educational material there is an audio presentation of the knowledge object. (Principle of Personalization)
H.8	In the educational material, the audio presentation style is learner friendly. (Principle of Voice)
H.9	In the educational material, a friendly character (avatar) appears that enhances the learning process of the trainees. (Top of Image)
H.10	In the educational material, the presentation of the knowledge object is done in parts. (Principle of Partition)
H.11	In the educational material there are interactive activities that provide feedback to the learners. (Principle of Personalization)
H.12	In the educational material there are long texts for the presentation of the cognitive object. (Principle of Partition)
H.13	The educational material provides clear instructions to the trainees for the implementation of the activities and tasks. (Principle of Signaling)
H.14	In the educational material there are marking elements (bold writing, underlining, coloring, etc.). (Principle of Signaling)
H.15	In the educational material there are introductory activities that help to study the cognitive object. (Principle of Pre-Education)
9th Axis: Th. General Notes	
I1	What do you think are the three strongest elements of the training material?
I2	Write up to three changes you suggest to improve the training material.

Table 3 PE70 Teacher Survey — Research Axes

1st Axis: Response to the goals of the Study Program
2nd Axis: Content Validity
3rd Axis: General remarks

Table 4 PE70 Teacher Survey – Research Axes – Questions in Each Axis

1st Axis: Response to the goals of the Study Program	
A1	To what extent can the user, with the help of the educational material, get to know the myths that refer to the life and the most important achievements of Theseus.
A2	To what extent the user can, with the help of the educational material, get to know Daedalus and Icarus.
A3	To what extent the user through the educational material can understand concepts related to the unit such as: hero, feat.
2nd Axis: Content Validity	
B1	How valid do you consider the information contained in the educational material. Explain your point.
B2	To what extent the activities of the educational material relate to the expected learning outcomes.
3rd Axis: General remarks	
C1	In your opinion, what are the three strongest elements of the training material?
C2	Write up to three changes you suggest to improve the training material.
C3	Write 2 reasons why you would or would not use the Educational material.

In this particular research, the coding and processing of the data was done with the technique of qualitative content analysis. The unit of analysis was the word set with semantic independence. In order to process the data, the categories per axis were determined. During the processing of the data, the anonymity of the participants was completely respected.

4.5 Limitations — Suggestions for Future Research

There were two limitations in this particular research. The first is the non-use of the educational material by students even though the educational material was designed for them. Also, the second limitation lies in the small sample of teachers who were asked to answer the questionnaire (qualitative research) evaluating the educational material. This results in the conclusions not being generalizable to the wider population of Primary Education teachers. The specific educational material could in the future be applied as supplementary material by teachers in order to teach the specific section of History.

The research could also be conducted on 3rd grade students so that the EY can be evaluated by them. It is proposed to create two groups of students, two different departments, where in one department (control group) teaching will be done in the conventional way and in the other department (experimental group) teaching will be done using educational material . Then follow the comparison of the learning results.

Finally, this research could be conducted on a larger number of teachers so that the conclusions can be generalized.

5. Research Conclusions

The first research question asked was whether the educational material is governed by the principles and methodology of distance education. The three distance education experts judged that the educational material is governed by the principles and methodology of Distance Education, namely:

- Scientific coherence/documentation of educational material

In the educational material there is scientific coherence and documentation since it is bibliographically documented with various sources for further study, with interpretation and critical discussion of the information. Comparative analysis of the information is absent due to the age group to which the educational material is addressed.

- The educational material contributes to the simple and understandable presentation of the knowledge object

They claim that the writing style is quite reader-friendly. Both personal and possessive pronouns are used with colloquial language and legible writing with correct font size. There is no information density and the presentation of the educational material is done in sections. They pointed out that there is little text that is combined with images, while it is enriched with many images and videos. Finally, the color compositions provide comfortable and pleasant navigation.

- Ease of use of educational material

In the educational material there is ease of use as the buttons and icons are understandable and recognizable and navigation is done with ease. In addition, the use of hyperlinks has credibility since it leads to the expected content.

- The educational system supports — guides the student in his study

The educational material is supportive and guiding in the student's study because there are advisory videos on how to study, emphasis is placed on points that are necessary and an avatar helps with his explanatory comments.

- The educational material supports the interaction with the learner in his study

The educational material supports the learner through activities to express themselves on important issues. However, activities involving emotional involvement and formulating one's own questions are absent due to the age group of users. Nevertheless, there are activities where the learner exchanges opinions with his peers, considering himself part of a social group, encouraging him to enrich his opinions through them.

- The educational material provides the possibility of reflection — self-evaluation for the learner

The educational material with the activities of self-evaluation, development of autonomous critical thinking, development of communication channels with the aim of feedback, correlation of new data with one's own (student's) reality and application to this new knowledge provides the user with the possibility of reflection and self-evaluation.

- Purpose — Expected results

The purpose and expected results are clearly stated in each teaching unit. In addition, both at the level of attitudes and knowledge and skills, there is motivation for the trainee. Finally based on the expected results the user can check his progress.

The second research question asked was whether the educational material has been created according to the Principles of Multimedia Learning. The three experts on distance education judged that it is in line with these principles, namely:

- Educational material in accordance with the Principles of Multimedia Learning

All educational material is based on the Principles of Multimedia Learning since the minimal text is combined with images that help to understand the cognitive object. Also, there are elements of narration, mainly with the friendly avatar while there is no information unrelated to the content. The language throughout the educational material is kept friendly by using the second person. In addition, the friendly style of the audio presentation and the use of a friendly avatar enhance the learning process. In addition, the use of long texts is absent, while clear instructions for the preparation of activities, labeling elements and introductory activities are diffused throughout the educational material.

- General Notes

As general remarks, the Distance Education experts judged that the strongest points of the material are the appropriateness of the images for understanding the content, the explanatory and interactive videos, the uniformity of the teaching units, the continuous feedback in the activities, the versatility of the material, the well-edited multimedia and the friendliness of all the material. As changes, they do not suggest anything, considering the educational material to be complete, clear, easy to use, even, with continuous feedback and based on Mayer's Principles of Multimedia Learning.

The third research question that was asked was what are the opinions of Primary Education teachers about the educational material created for 3rd Primary students in the context of the cognitive object of the third unit of history entitled “Theseus”. The five teachers judged that the educational material meets the objectives of the Study Program and that there is validity in its content.

- Responding to the goals of the Study Program

The EY meets the goals of the Study Program since it covers the specific purposes of the Analytical Study Program of the specific module, regarding both Theseus and Daedalus and Icarus. In addition, the user has the possibility to understand concepts related to the unit either through the activities, the videos or the vocabulary subsection.

- Content validity

In the specific educational material, there is content validity since both the information contained was evaluated as valid, based on reliable sources, but also the activities are directly related to the expected learning outcomes, setting clear and unambiguous goals for each of them.

- General remarks

As general remarks, the five teachers judged that the strongest points of the teaching material are the clear definition of objectives, the very useful material per sub-unit, the interesting, varied, engaging and highly interactive activities, the interactive videos, the rich images, the videos with the teacher’s recorded voice, the comprehensible presentation of the information content of each unit in many different ways, the easy and understandable language, the feedback she uses in the activities, the correct amount of information and the creator’s aesthetic point of view regarding the presentation educational material. As improvement changes, three of the five participants in “Time for play” suggested that there be more interactive activities, in general the enrichment of the educational material with more activities, perhaps the existence of a navigation map in a visible place so that the learner knows where he is but also a helper at each point in the training material to remind the user what to do. Two of the five evaluators judged that the material does not need any improvement change because it meets the needs of the students regardless of their learning level. Finally, all five evaluators would use the specific educational material since they consider it easy to use, friendly, tasteful, responsive to the specific purposes of the module and attractive. An evaluator suggested the creation of such educational materials in various other modules for better understanding of the subject matter.

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